

Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie

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CCSA – Centro de Ciências Sociais e Aplicadas
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CCSA – Centro de Ciências Sociais e Aplicadas

Programa de Pós-Graduação em Controladoria e Finanças
Empresariais

NORMA OU MARCO REGULATÓRIO

Resposta à Audiência Pública - Discussion Paper and comment letters: Proposed Targeted Amendments to the IFRS Foundation Constitution to Accommodate an International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) to Set IFRS Sustainability Standards

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Como referenciar:

Geron, C. M. S.; Formigoni, H.; Farias, K. T. R.; Segura, L. C.; Nishimura, P. S.; Hanada, C. E. M.; Turra, J. F.; Yoshita, K.; Franzin, K.; Tanikawa, A.; Grecco, M. C. P. (2021). Resposta à Audiência Pública - Discussion Paper and comment letters: Proposed Targeted Amendments to the IFRS Foundation Constitution to Accommodate an International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) to Set IFRS Sustainability Standards. Norma ou Marco Regulatório. PPGCFTG da Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie. Grupo de Estudos em IFRS. DOI/10.5281/zenodo.10004933

Centro de Ciências Sociais e Aplicadas

Linha de Pesquisa: Finanças, regulação contábil e tributária

Projeto de extensão: Grupo de Estudos em IFRS

Produto Técnico-Tecnológico: Norma ou marco regulatório

Demanda espontânea: resposta à consulta pública da Fundação IFRS.

Organização: Demanda da Fundação IFRS, produzido pelo Grupo de Pesquisa em IFRS da Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie

Descrição do PPT: Resposta à Audiência Pública - Discussion Paper and comment letters: Proposed Targeted Amendments to the IFRS Foundation Constitution to Accommodate an International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) to Set IFRS Sustainability Standards.

Divulgação da Produção: A resposta à consulta pública foi enviada como resposta ao questionamento da Fundação IFRS. Sendo esta resposta um relatório derivado de um grupo de discussão e pesquisa, está disponível na plataforma Zenodo.

Aderência (Baixa, Média ou Alta): Alta. O relatório técnico é resultado de uma ampla discussão de normas contábeis internacionais desenvolvida pelo grupo de pesquisa em IFRS, consistindo em um resultado de formação de pessoas (alunos de graduação e pós graduação) e também proposições técnicas que podem afetar a todas as organizações.

Impacto Potencial: Médio. O resultado desta resposta técnica resultará em alterações das normas contábeis internacionais com potencial de impacto para todas as empresas no mundo que adotam o IFRS.

Impacto Realizado: Médio. O impacto de uma alteração de norma deve ser observado no futuro, com a implementação das sugestões feitas por esse grupo de pesquisa. Dessa forma, só será possível medir o impacto na efetiva implementação das alterações sugeridas.

Inovação (Baixa, Média ou Alta): Média. Uma alteração de norma contábil internacional sobre *International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB)* é uma inovação derivada de discussões para inserir nas normas a prática que já ocorre nas empresas e acomodar a sustentabilidade nestas normas. Portanto, a implementação efetiva desta norma sugere uma inovação para a área contábil e de produção de informações confiáveis para a estas entidades.

Complexidade (Baixa, Média ou Alta): Média. O produto requer um conhecimento técnico bastante abrangente em normas contábeis para que seja elaborado uma resposta técnica e cujo tema foi debatido em professores, alunos de mestrado e doutorado com diversas áreas de conhecimento técnico empresarial. Dessa forma, entende-se que a complexidade deste produto é média.

Aplicabilidade (Baixa, Média ou Alta): Alta. Aplicabilidade para todas as empresas.

Abrangência Potencial (Baixa, Média ou Alta): Alta. A norma terá aplicabilidade em todo o território nacional e internacional.

Abrangência realizada (Baixa, Média ou Alta): Alta. A norma terá aplicabilidade em todo o território nacional e internacional.

Replicabilidade (Restrita, Irrestrita ou Escalável): Irrestrita

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Resposta à Audiência Pública - Discussion Paper and comment letters: Proposed Targeted Amendments to the IFRS Foundation Constitution to Accommodate an International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) to Set IFRS Sustainability Standards

RESUMO

O produto desenvolvido teve por objetivo responder à consulta pública referente à Proposed Targeted Amendments to the IFRS Foundation Constitution to Accommodate an International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) to Set IFRS Sustainability Standards.

Palavras-chave: sustentabilidade, norma, IFRS Standards

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Response to Public Consultation: Discussion Paper and comment letters: Proposed Targeted Amendments to the IFRS Foundation Constitution to Accommodate an International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) to Set IFRS Sustainability Standards

ABSTRACT

The product was carried out aimed to respond to the public consultation regarding the Proposed Targeted Amendments to the IFRS Foundation Constitution to Accommodate an International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) to Set IFRS Sustainability Standards.

Keywords: sustainability, standards, IFRS standards

Como referenciar:

Geron, C. M S; Formigoni, H; Farias, K. T. R.; Segura, L C.; Nishimura, P. S; Hanada, C. E. M.; Turra, J. F; Yoshita, K.; Franzin K.; Tanikawa, A.; Grecco, M. C. P. (2021). Resposta à Audiência Pública - Discussion Paper and comment letters: Proposed Targeted Amendments to the IFRS Foundation Constitution to Accommodate an International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) to Set IFRS Sustainability Standards. Norma ou Marco Regulatório. PPGCFTG da Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie. Grupo de Estudos em IFRS. DOI/10.5281/zenodo.10004933

Carta Apresentada ao IFRS em 10/07/2021

IFRS Foundation
The IFRS Foundation Trustees
Columbus Building 7
Westferry Circus
Canary Wharf
London E14 4HD
United Kingdom

Reference: Proposed Targeted Amendments to the IFRS Foundation Constitution to Accommodate an International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) to Set IFRS Sustainability Standards

Mackenzie Presbyterian University and the “Associação Nacional dos Executivos de Finanças, Administração e Contabilidade” - ANEFAC appreciate the opportunity to provide comments to the Proposed Targeted Amendments to the IFRS Foundation Constitution to Accommodate an International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) to Set IFRS Sustainability Standards.

In its professional postgraduate program in Accounting and Corporate Finance, Mackenzie Presbyterian University established a study group on International Accounting Standards. One of its objectives is to discuss and present proposals to standard-setting bodies’ public consultation.

Anefac is a body engaged in the improvement and professional development of our associates and executives. We share professional experience, build relationships, and encourage research and continuing education in finance, management, and accounting issues.

Our responses are based on the opinion of the working group composed of accounting professionals and academics.

The authors of this document are Cecília Moraes Santostaso Geron, Liliane Cristina Segura, Henrique Formigoni, Kelly Teixeira Rodrigues Farias, Patrícia Satomi Nishimura, Carlos Eduardo Mori Hanada, Marta Cristina Pelucio Grecco, Karen Franzin, José Francisco Turra, Alice Tanikawa, Kenzo Yoshita.

Yours sincerely,

Cecília Moraes Santostaso Geron
Professor at postgraduate program in Accounting and Corporate Finance
Mackenzie Presbyterian University

Relatório apresentado à Consulta Pública

Director of International Accounting Standards at Anefac

Question 1

Do you agree that the amendments proportionately reflect the Trustees' strategic direction, considering in particular:

- (a) the proposed amendments to the objectives of the Foundation, outlined in the proposed new section 2b of the *Constitution*, as set out in Appendix A; and
- (b) the proposed amendments to reflect the structure and function of the new board, outlined in the proposed new sections 43–56 of the *Constitution*, as set out in Appendix A?

(a) Yes, we agree with the proposed amendments to the objectives of the Foundation, outlined in the proposed new section 2b of the Constitution, as set out in Appendix A.

(b) No, we don't agree with section 45. We suggest an equitable distribution of members. In section 45 item (e) we propose added a proportion between the countries. Despite having shares in stock exchanges in the most developed financial markets, multinational entities have subsidiaries on all continents. Thus, the number of representatives among the regions should be better distributed, cooperating to minimize the differences in information with the experiences of each country.

It is essential to ensure that information about all continents is disclosed by entities regardless of the market where the companies' shares are traded. It is very common in South America that information about climate effects in these countries is deliberately disclosed only in other markets.

South African companies, publicly traded on the Johannesburg stock exchanges, are pioneers in Integrated Reporting. The King Code III (2009), corporate governance regulation, requires companies listed on the Johannesburg stock exchange to prepare the integrated report annually or provide reasons for not doing so. These companies demonstrated the main items requested by Integrated Report¹. Research proved with 246 Integrated Report of South Africa, over three years, 2011 to 2013, following the Integrated Reporting requirement in South Africa, a significant increase in the extent and quality of Integrated Reporting practice².

Besides, we believe that the new board should include representation of all stakeholders impacted by the activities of the entities that report. Members of the new board should have technical expertise.

Question 2

On the potential naming of the new board and its associated standards, do you agree that ‘the International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB)’ setting ‘IFRS sustainability standards’ accurately describes the function of the new board and its associated standards?

Yes, we agree that ‘the International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB)’ setting ‘IFRS sustainability standards’ accurately describes the function of the new board and its associated standards. However, we believe that the declared users of this information would be stakeholders and not only investors and other capital market participants.

¹ Rivera-Arrubla, Y. A., Zorio-Grima, A., & García-Benau, M. A. (2017). Integrated Reports: Disclosure level and explanatory factors. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 13(1), 155–176. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SRJ-02-2016-0033>

² Ahmed Haji, A., & Anifowose, M. (2016). The trend of integrated reporting practice in South Africa: ceremonial or substantive? *Sustainability Accounting, Management and Policy Journal*, 7(2), 190–224. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SAMPJ-11-2015-0106>

Question 3

Do you agree with this proposed consequential amendment, outlined in proposed new sections 60 and 61 of the Constitution, as set out in Appendix A?

Yes, we agree with this proposed consequential amendment, outlined in proposed new sections 60 and 61 of the Constitution, as set out in Appendix A. We believe that expertise in sustainability reporting and sustainable development must be mandatory.

Question 4

Are there any other matters you would like to raise in relation to the proposed targeted amendments to the Constitution?

We would like to raise the importance of academic researchers in contributing to the standards process development and analysis. Besides, it is fundamental to have sustainability reporting experts on the Board and, possibly, professionals from intergovernmental entities.

A topic that we believe would be better defined is the relation with other entities, such as GRI, besides the connection with intergovernmental organizations whose principles or rules need to be included in the standards of ISSB.

REFERÊNCIAS BIBLIOGRÁFICAS

Ahmed Haji, A., & Anifowose, M. (2016). The trend of integrated reporting practice in South Africa: ceremonial or substantive? *Sustainability Accounting, Management and Policy Journal*, 7(2), 190–224. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SAMPJ-11-2015-0106>

Rivera-Arrubla, Y. A., Zorio-Grima, A., & García-Benau, M. A. (2017). Integrated Reports: Disclosure level and explanatory factors. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 13(1), 155–176. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SRJ-02-2016-0033>

DECLARAÇÃO DO ESTRATO DO PTT.

Transformação causada pelo produto técnico/tecnológico no ambiente (organização, comunidade, localidade, etc.) ao qual se destina. Necessário declarar o motivo da criação, a relevância da questão do demandante e o foco de aplicação do produto. Avalia-se o impacto potencial e realizado do produto ao ambiente de transformação ao que se destina.											
Critério de avaliação	Realizado			Potencial			Replicável			TOTAL	
	Descrição	Pontos	Pond.	Descrição	Pontos	Pond.	Descrição	Pontos	Pond.	Pontos	Pond.
IMPACTO (Peso: 25%)	Pontos Ausência de impacto	10	6,0	Pontos Ausência de impacto	10,0	4				10,0	16,7
APLICABILIDADE (Peso: 25%)	Pontos Não aplicada	10	4,0	Pontos Não aplicável	10,0	2	Pontos Não Replicável	10	4,0	10,0	16,7
INOVAÇÃO (Peso: 25%)	Sem inovação	15	15,0							15,0	25,0
COMPLEXIDADE (Peso: 25%)	Pontos Não complexo	10	10,0							10,0	16,7
Estrato								TA2	Pontuação	75,0	